

Evaluation of Bond Lengths of Hydrogen Bonds

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The bond lengths of some hydrogen bonds have been evaluated using Roy's^{1,2} relation. It has been observed that the length between H and Y in the X-H...Y bond in general, is higher by 10 to 15% than the observed length when the bond is assumed to be linear. It is concluded that the hydrogen bond is non-linear with a bend at H, in agreement with experimental observations.

The bond length of a diatomic species can be obtained from a knowledge of its symmetrical stretching frequency.^{1,3} Almost nothing* has been till now published on the theoretical estimation of the bond length of hydrogen bonds.

As a further contribution to the knowledge of the hydrogen bond a short discussion of the results on some frequently observed hydrogen bonds basing on previous work^{1,3} has been reported here.

Bond Length—frequency relationship for a hydrogen bond: Bond length frequency relation^{1,3} when applied to the di-atoms of the bonds in X-H.....Y, gives for X—H bond

$$y_1 = \frac{A(m_x + m_h)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{L_1^3 n_1} \quad \dots (1)$$

where y_1 is the frequency, L_1 the bond length and m_x and m_h the atomic masses of X and H, and for bond H...Y,

$$y_2 = \frac{A(m_h + m_y)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{L_2^3 n_2} \quad \dots (2)$$

where y_2 is the frequency, L_2 the bond length and m_h and m_y the atomic masses of H and Y.

For the X-H.....Y bond of length L and stretching frequency y , the bond length frequency relation would be

$$y = \frac{A(m_x + m_h)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{L_1^3 n_1} - \frac{A(m_h + m_y)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{L_2^3 n_2} \quad \dots (3)$$

From relation 3, it may be noticed that the bond length H...Y can be determined if the frequency y and the length L are known.

Use of spectroscopic data: Table 1 shows some frequently observed representative hydrogen bonds and contains values of symmetrical stretching frequency y , observed bond

* The only work that has received some attention is that due to Lippincott and Schroeder (1957).

lengths of X-H and H...Y bonds and calculated bond lengths of H...Y bond through relation 3. (Nakamoto 1955).

TABLE 1

Frequency and bond length values of various hydrogen bonds

No.	Bond	Compound	ν (cm) ⁻¹	L (Å)	L (Å)	L (Å)	L (Å)
			X-H...Y	X-H...Y	X-H	H...Y(obs)	H...Y(Cal)
1	O-H...O	Diaspore	2967	2.71	0.96	1.75	2.05
		α -HIO ₃	2778	2.686	0.99	1.696	1.96
		Formic acid	3080	2.73	0.96	1.77	2.05
		(COOH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1900	2.518	1.057	1.433	1.69
		(COOH) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	3460	2.85	0.96	1.89	2.22
2	O-H...Cl	Hydroxyl amine HCl	2898	2.99	0.96	2.03	2.33
		Chloral hydrate	3333	3.15	0.96	2.19	2.29
3	O-H...N	Cyclohexanoxime	3144	2.75	0.98	1.805	2.13
		<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldoxime	3190	2.82	0.97	1.85	2.18
4	N-H...N	Melamine	3279	3.00	1.038	1.962	2.33
		Hexamethylene diamine	3344	3.21	1.038	2.172	2.49
5	N-H...O	Urea	3350	3.02	1.038	1.982	2.31
		Sym-trinitro benzene	3436	3.10	1.038	2.062	2.39
6	N-H...F	NH ₃ BF ₃	3338	3.01	1.038	1.972	2.26
		N ₂ H ₄ ·2HF	2548	2.62	1.038	1.582	1.79
7	F-H...F	(HF) _n	3440	2.55	0.917	1.633	1.99
		KHF ₂	1450	2.26	0.917	1.343	1.44

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The observed bond lengths of H...Y bond is obtained assuming that the bond X-H...Y is linear. It is seen that the calculated H...Y bond length in all cases is 10 to 15% higher than that of the observed. This discrepancy can be explained if we consider the X-H...Y bond to be non-linear, a conclusion which in some cases has been confirmed from spectroscopic and neutron diffraction studies of molecules containing hydrogen bonds, and thus, lends support to the view that a bond X-H...Y in general, is non-linear with a bend at the hydrogen atom. The critical test of locating definitely an individual hydrogen atom in a structure, closer to one than the other can be carried out by means of diffraction of neutrons.

Albrecht *et al*⁴ and Marsh⁷ have shown that the structure of glycine in crystalline state has a bifurcated hydrogen bond $\text{-N} \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \text{O} \\ \searrow \text{O} \end{array}$ involving the -NH_2^+ group, and this has been verified (Burns⁸) from neutron diffraction studies. Similar bifurcated bonds have also been inferred

(Rogers¹¹) in crystals of iodic acid, HIO_3 and (Beevers²) in nitramide, NH_2NO_2 . These bifurcated bonds involve non-linear hydrogen bonds.

In penterythritol, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_4$ crystal Hvoslef⁶ have found an angle of 6° between the directions of $\text{O}-\text{H}$ and $\text{O}\dots\text{O}$, from neutron diffraction study giving a bend in the hydrogen bond of 9° . The hydrogen bond bends the molecules into layers. In diaspore AlHO_2 a deviation of the $\text{O}-\text{H}$ bond by 12° from $\text{O}\dots\text{O}$ has been observed (Busing⁴).

In the structure of oxalic acid dihydrate Cox *et al*⁵ have shown that each water molecule has three hydrogen bonds directed from it to the oxygens of different carbonyl groups; two of these are about equal at 2.87 and 2.84\AA while the third is 2.52\AA . The shortest known hydrogen bond length between two oxygen atoms of $2.40 \pm 0.02\text{\AA}$ is found in the crystals of acetamide hemihydrochloride, $(\text{NH}_2\text{COCH}_3)_2 \text{HCl}$.

The two equal peaks observed for tetrabromo catechol at 6820 and 6920 cm^{-1} corresponding to the structure

involving an intramolecular hydrogen bond formation could only spatially permit the possibility of bend $\text{O}-\text{H}\dots\text{O}$ and $\text{O}-\text{H}\dots\text{Br}$ bonds in the molecule. A good deal of information obtained from recent study of polypeptides and proteins in their crystalline states show that the $\text{N}-\text{H}\dots\text{O}$ bend at H is within 10° .

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The above experimental evidences of a few bend X-H.....Y bends along with the observation is a few cases of strong and weak hydrogen bonds clearly show that the X-H...Y bond is non-linear. As for example the O-H...O bond in pentherythritol can be represented diagrammatically as

In NH_3 molecule the N-H...N distance is $3.38 \pm 0.04 \text{ \AA}$ giving a weak bond while in NH_4N_3 the N-H...N distance is 2.94 \AA giving rise to a strong bond. That the frequency of a hydrogen bond stretching mode $\nu(\text{O} \dots \text{O})$ is dependent on the strength of the hydrogen bond has been recently shown by Rasch¹⁰ who isolated two polymorphic forms of phenol in solid state, and obtained both mid- and far- infrared spectra of each form.

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